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Analysis

Valuing diversification benefits through intercropping in Mediterranean agroecosystems: A choice experiment approach

Francisco Alcon^{a,*}, Cristina Marín-Miñano^a, José A. Zabala^a, María-Dolores de-Miguel^a, José M. Martínez-Paz^b

^a Departamento de Economía de la Empresa, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería Agronómica, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Paseo Alfonso XIII, 48, 30203 Cartagena, Spain

^b Departamento de Economía Aplicada, Facultad de Economía y Empresa, Universidad de Murcia, Campus de Espinardo, 30100 Murcia Spain

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ABSTRACT

The agricultural sector faces a series of environmental challenges such as water and soil pollution, erosion or biodiversity loss, especially in monoculture systems. Alternatively, crop diversification is seen as an option to reduce negative impacts and to enhance agricultural Ecosystem Services (ES). Most of these ES, such as improving resilience, despite the benefits and the high social value, do not take part in the market. In this context, the present paper presents an analysis of social preferences regarding crop diversification practices in Mediterranean agroecosystems. To do so, a choice experiment has been developed to assess social demand for more welfare-improving agricultural cropping systems. Benefits were obtained from improving environmental and cultural ES provision due to intercropping, as crop diversification practices. The results show a strong social preference for crop diversification with regard to all the benefits considered in the experiment. In fact, the total economic value for non-market goods and services provided by intercropping, which ranges from 900 to 1400 €/ha/year, for some crops might be potentially higher than cropland financial benefits. These results highlight the social support for a change in agricultural model to reach sustainable agroecosystems, which is essential to ensure the success of agrarian and rural development policies.

1. Introduction

The steep growth in world population during the last centuries has led to changes in food production (Tilman et al., 2002). In agriculture, its most evident consequence is monoculture, which prevails over other agricultural practices, despite deriving in a depletion of biodiversity and resilience (Trewavas, 2002). Thus, agriculture currently faces important environmental challenges, beyond the growing food demand (Tilman et al., 2011). Some of these challenges are the adaptation to climate change (Thornton, 2012) or the management of negative externalities derived from some agricultural practices, including biodiversity loss, waterways and waterbodies pollution or high greenhouse gases emissions (Smil, 2000; Diaz and Rosenberg, 2008; Foley et al., 2011; Vermeulen et al., 2012). Therefore, many actors are demanding a change in current farming systems to increase agroecosystems sustainability, food security and to prevent irreparable environmental impacts (Tilman et al., 2002; MEA, 2005; Foley et al., 2011; IPES-Food, 2016). Consequently, the latest Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) reforms have included sustainable focused actions such as crop

diversification in the *greening* context (Dessart et al., 2019).

Many suggestions have been proposed for optimising agriculture both in economic as well as environmental terms. These suggestions include organic farming, precision agriculture or no-till practices (Trewavas, 2002; Flores and Sarandon, 2004). Another alternative to intensive monoculture is crop diversification, which refers to a maintenance of “multiple sources of production, and varying what is produced across farming landscapes (intercropping) and over time (crop rotation)” (IPES-Food, 2016). In this sense, crop diversification can promote soil quality conservation, biodiversity, pest control or crop resilience (Kremen and Miles, 2012; Jarecki et al., 2018; Hunt et al., 2019). Furthermore, crop diversification can provide a way to address the social and environmental challenges currently faced by agriculture (Badgley et al., 2007; Kleijn et al., 2009; Kremen and Miles, 2012) and to mitigate the effects of climate change (Lin, 2011). Crop diversification may be implemented by several alternatives, such as cover crops, crop rotation, intercropping or agroforestry (Wezel et al., 2014). While the use of cover crops and crop rotations may produce trade-offs between environmental and economic benefits (e.g. cover crops may

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: francisco.alcon@upct.es (F. Alcon).

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enhance biodiversity while reducing the main crop yield), intercropping practices seem to generate win-win solutions (Rosa-Schleich et al., 2019). Indeed, intercropping is associated with an increase in soil organic carbon without negative effects being found on crop yield in Mediterranean agricultural areas (Morugán-Coronado et al., 2020). These facts, together with the case study characteristics, have encouraged us to select intercropping as the crop diversification practice to be assessed. Thus, intercropping, defined as “the coexistence of two or more crops in the same field at the same time” (Wezel et al., 2014), can specifically promote both food security and environmental health in large-scale and industrialized farming (Fung et al., 2019; Rosa-Schleich et al., 2019).

Nevertheless, alternative farming systems must be carefully assessed to ensure their viability. Hence, an interdisciplinary approach for this assessment is the Ecosystem Services (ES) framework. ES are benefits derived from ecosystems and received by society (Costanza et al., 1997; Daily, 1997). Within agroecosystems, the most evident ES are the supply of food, fibre and fodder. Nevertheless, these ecosystems also provide regulating and cultural ES, such as CO₂ capture or cultural heritage, respectively (TEEB, 2010). In fact, the provision of ES, and also disservices (EDS), by an agroecosystem depends on the management practises to be carried out (Zhang et al., 2007). EDS, as opposed to ES, are defined as the perceived or actual negative contributions of agroecosystems on human welfare (Shackleton et al., 2016). Therefore, high-input practises involve EDS generation, such as soil degradation or the increase of nutrients in water bodies, which can affect adjacent ecosystems such as rivers or lakes (Tilman et al., 2002). On the other hand, monoculture is strongly linked to biodiversity loss (Foley et al., 2005; IPES-Food, 2016), while sustainable agriculture, such as organic or diversified farming enhances the richness and abundance of species (Bengtsson et al., 2005). Sustainable agriculture aims to provide enough food for a growing population without compromising the environment and farmers' livelihoods (Wezel et al., 2014).

However, due to the fact that many ES lack a market value (Sandhu et al., 2015), and thus there is a lack of farmers' incentives to adopt crop diversification (Lin, 2011), this agricultural practice is scarcely spread among the EU farms. At policy level, the CAP, established in the middle of the 20th century, aimed to promote agricultural management measures focused on production maximisation (ensuring demand) and market situation (improving the farmers' financial situation). Since 1992, the CAP has been adapted to the emerging challenges faced by EU citizens, including the environment, food safety, animal and plant health and animal welfare. Real environmental practices were effectively introduced into the CAP from the Agenda 2000, and enforced by the 2003 reform, introducing both cross-compliance for direct payments (first pillar of the CAP) and agri-environmental schemes (second pillar of the CAP). These mechanisms aimed to maintain the land in good agricultural and environmental conditions and represented the first attempts to make the CAP more sustainable. Cross-compliance made the single payments conditional on good agricultural and environmental criteria, such as practices to prevent soil erosion, maintain soil organic matter and permanent grasslands, protect biodiversity and ensure water quality (EC, 2019). Additionally, the 2013 reform (Reg. EU/1305, 2013) introduced a new green direct payment, generally called greening, associated with the payment in the first pillar. Greening aims to support environmental and climate helpful actions developed by farmers, applying a subsidy of up to 30% of direct payment. These actions were included as an economic instrument to reward farmers for preserving natural resources and providing public goods, which are benefits to the public that are not reflected in market prices. To receive the greening direct payment, farmers need to comply with three mandatory practices: maintain permanent grassland, establish ecological focus areas to safeguard and improve farm biodiversity, and crop diversification. The former practices imply having more than one crop per farm, with intercropping not being considered explicitly. The second pillar of the CAP enhances agri-environment measures to

encourage biodiversity and the provision of ES, but with a non-mandatory basis for farmers. Within these voluntary practices, crop diversification is also collected by some practices already included in some agri-environment schemes, such as cover crops. In other words, the CAP has evolved according to European conditions, including crop diversification actions to be adopted by the farmers.

The economic benefits of crop diversification as well as its potential positive impacts on human welfare are unknown, unless they are influenced by the socioeconomic context within a productive region. In this framework, a means to quantify social support is the use of stated preferences methods based on the generation of a hypothetical market according to consumers' preferences (Hoyos, 2010). Moreover, considering the socioeconomic context and relying on society's support are essential tools to reinforce management policies (Castro et al., 2011). To date, some works have addressed agricultural ES valuation in different production systems (Aslam et al., 2017; Houessionon et al., 2017; Novikova et al., 2017; Rodríguez-Entrena et al., 2012; Bernués et al., 2014; García-Llorente et al., 2012; Martínez-Paz et al., 2019). Although some of these authors have employed state preferences methodologies, the approach of using the ES framework remains uncommon (Bernués et al., 2014; García-Llorente et al., 2012). Most of these works sustain that ES values stated by society can be higher than market goods in many agroecosystems (Sandhu et al., 2008). However, none of the previous works have focused on ES valuation within diversified agroecosystems, despite crop diversification having been proven to have both environmental as well as social benefits (Badgley et al., 2007; Kleijn et al., 2009; Kremen and Miles, 2012; Jarecki et al., 2018; Hunt et al., 2019).

In this context, the aim of the current work is to estimate the value of ES provided by crop diversification focused on intercropping practices in the case of the Region of Murcia (South-East Spain) by using a choice experiment approach. This case study, beyond its particular interest, is representative of the agricultural production system of many Mediterranean agroecosystems, in which extensive rainfed systems coexist with intensified irrigated crops. Additionally, the implemented choice experiment would be used to validate the relevance of ES flow influenced by intercropping crop diversification.

In short, it remains necessary to delve into diversification implications (Kremen and Miles, 2012), globally as well as into particular cases, where social, economic and environmental spheres are analysed in great depth. The susceptibility of ES in the Mediterranean basin means that the implementation of diversification practices becomes a key policy option for agricultural decision-makers (Lee et al., 2019). The novelty of the present work is that it addresses the ES valuation of intercropping practices using choice experiments, which allows to value not only the overall contribution of intercropping to human welfare but also the welfare provided by specific ES involved diversified agroecosystems. Hence, this study contributes to enhancing the knowledge regarding agroecosystem ES flows valuation in intercropping diversified crops, which can be potentially used by public managers to guide agricultural policies aimed to promote resources sustainability.

2. Methodology

2.1. Case study

The case study is located in the Region of Murcia (South-East of Spain) (Fig. 1). The co-existence of good-quality soils, a semi-arid Mediterranean climate and water resources, both surface and groundwater, has fostered the development of one of the most productive irrigated farming systems in Europe. The average precipitation is 400 mm/year, although with a strong variability in space and time. Permanent woody crops occupy the greater part of the agricultural area of the region, with the presence of citrus and stone fruits being prevalent in irrigated areas and almond trees in rain-fed areas. (Martínez-Paz et al., 2018).

Fig. 1. Study area.

In the irrigated agroecosystem, based on intensive monocropping, traditional farming systems have been gradually substituted by modern systems leading to higher productivity and decreasing the quantity and variety of the ES provided by the agroecosystem as a whole (Romero and Melo, 2015).

Crop diversification implementation is a way to improve ES provision by agroecosystems. In the study area, intercropping and crop rotation are the most feasible diversification practices. This work will focus on intercropping, which is indeed the only diversification alternative with woody crops. Intercropping diversification consists in the simultaneous implementation of two or more crops within a field, with at least one of them being a woody crop in this case. This diversification can provide not only a second product but can also help to solve environmental problems in almonds orchards by reducing soil erosion or enhancing soil quality. On the other hand, in irrigated citrus orchards, crop diversification can potentially provide natural nitrogen fixation (reducing fertiliser application) or greater CO₂ sequestration by the crop, as examples (Aguilera et al., 2013). Intercropping is uncommon in the study area, but it can be found in traditional agroecosystems in a good conservation status. At a larger scale, intercropping is hard to find, despite it having been incentivised by the European Union's CAP.

2.2. Experimental design

Choice Experiment (CE) is a stated preference method based on Lancaster's multiattribute utility theory (Lancaster, 1966) and the random utility theory (McFadden, 1974). According to them, the utility provided by a good or service can be decomposed into the sum of the utility provided by the attributes which compose it (Lancaster, 1966). Thus, an individual will choose an alternative accordingly to maximise his/her utility level (McFadden, 1974). This method allows to analyse the provision of the attributes (and their levels) within goods and the relationships between these attributes (Bateman et al., 2002). In this case, CE allows a valuation of different ES within an agroecosystem, as well as the perceived added value which is provided by intercropping practises. CE is implemented through four stages (Hoyos, 2010): (1) both the attributes and their levels are defined and established; (2) choice sets are selected; (3) the structure and assembly of the questionnaire are set up; and (4) data are collected. These stages are extended below.

Attributes for the CE development were selected through a literature review and expert consultation, on the basis of the expected ES changes due to intercropping practices in agroecosystems within the semiarid Mediterranean areas. Intercropping practices may contribute to a variety of ES, such as food production, pollination, pest control, biodiversity, soil health, or carbon sequestration, among others (Martin-Guay et al., 2018). Specifically, the attributes selected for the final design covered environmental benefits, such as biodiversity, erosion control and carbon sequestration, as well as socio-cultural benefits, like the maintenance of cultural heritage and landscape aesthetics. As the experts stated, these environmental benefits were chosen due to the contribution of intercropping practices in overcoming major agricultural challenges nowadays: biodiversity loss, land degradation and

climate change mitigation, respectively. Regarding the socio-cultural benefits, intercropping systems are seen as a part of the cultural heritage and landscape of the case study, which claims to be conserved as the remains of traditional agroecosystems (Martínez-Paz et al., 2019). Attributes are referred to regulating and cultural ES, which do not participate directly in the market. Biodiversity, which is not itself an ES but it is also considered due to its importance in maintaining the good status of an ecosystem (TEEB, 2010). On the other hand, provisioning services were excluded from the attributes list since they are covered by market valuation, and in order to avoid double accounting in global agroecosystem valuation (Fisher et al., 2009). Lack of biophysical information frequently complicates the selection of attributes indicators. Moreover, the indicators must be understandable for the target population that participate in the valuation process (Perni and Martínez-Paz, 2017).

With regard to the expected impact of intercropping practices on society and the environment, proxy indicators were used due to the lack of reliable information available about the specific levels in the area. Thus, it is expected that diversification practices would increase biodiversity (Rodríguez-Ortega et al., 2016; Novikova et al., 2017; Dupras et al., 2017; Grilli et al., 2018; Varela et al., 2018). Specifically, a maximum percentage increment of microbial richness of 15% over non-diversified practices is to be expected, according to Venter et al. (2016) estimations. A reduction in the rate of soil erosion can also be expected compared to monocropping. Erosion rates of 4 t/ha year can be found in the area (Verschaeren et al., 2019), which can be reduced to 1 t/ha year under the intercropping farming system. With this consideration and taking into account Hunt et al. (2019), De Vente et al. (2007) and Boix-Fayos et al. (2005) estimations, the expected percentage of erosion reduction achieved with the intercropping system has been set at 94%. Diversification practices also have an impact on the crop carbon balance. Agricultural practices have also been shown to affect soil organic carbon sequestration (West and Post, 2002). Thus, the percentage of soil organic carbon increment has been employed as a proxy indicator by using the Aguilera et al. (2013, 2015) estimations for Mediterranean agroecosystem practices.

It is also expected that diversification practices would have an impact on the cultural ES. Expert consultation enabled the main cultural ES affected by intercropping to be identified. Cultural heritage would be enhanced because traditional knowledge is an essential tool when adapting diversification to local edaphoclimatic conditions (Swiderska et al., 2011). On the other hand, the landscape would be more assorted due several species co-existing (Rodríguez-Ortega et al., 2016; Jourdain and Vivithkeyoonvong, 2017; Novikova et al., 2017; Dupras et al., 2017; Varela et al., 2018).

Selected attributes and their preliminary levels defined were validated through a pilot survey to 15 individuals randomly selected in order to verify their understanding of the indicators. The final list of attributes and their corresponding levels are shown in Table 1. It is important to note that the landscape attribute is considered as a cultural ES to capture the utility provided by the landscape aesthetic aspect.

Regarding the cost attribute, the economic contribution was included in the choice experiment design to determine the increase in

Table 1
Attributes and levels of the choice set.

Attribute	Indicator	Description	Levels
Biodiversity (BIOD)	Increment in soil microbial richness	Expected % of soil microbial richness	0 ^{SQ}
		increment over monocropping	7.5
			15
Erosion (ERO)	Reduction in soil erosion	Expected % of soil erosion rates reduction over monocropping	0 ^{SQ}
			47
			94
Carbon balance (CARBON)	Increment of soil organic carbon annually	Expected % of soil organic carbon per hectare and year	0 ^{SQ}
		increase over monocropping	25
			50
Cultural heritage (HERIT)	Traditional agricultural practices	Maintenance of traditional agricultural practices	Absence ^{SQ}
			Presence
Diverse Landscape (LAND)	Landscape beauty	Perception of agricultural landscape beauty	Single crop ^{SQ}
			Multiple crops
Cost (COST)	Economic contribution	Increase in foodstuff expenditure (€/month)	10
			20
		per household (fruit and vegetable consumption)	30
			40
			50

^{SQ} Status Quo: Intensive monocropping system.

foodstuff expenditure per family derived from the willingness to consume products from diversified farming. The cost attribute levels were selected taking the monthly average expenditure in fruits, vegetables and cereals per family as a reference, valued at about 100€ (MAPA, 2018). Thus, five cost levels were defined, which imply considering an increase in foodstuff expenditure ranging from 10% to 50%.

The *Ngene 1.0.2* software package (Rose et al., 2010) was used to combine selected attributes and their different levels within the analysed farming systems by means of an s-efficiency design for the pilot survey and a Bayesian design for the final survey. In the case of the final survey, the Bayesian efficient design was the best suited in order to ensure efficient results, since the sample was large enough for its development. The final design comprised 20 choice sets which were blocked in 4 groups. Different choice set blocks were randomly distributed among the respondents. Regarding the CE questions, the choice sets combined two intercropping alternatives with the monocrop SQ alternative, and different choice set blocks were randomly distributed among the respondents. They were asked to choose one alternative for each of the five choice sets presented. Fig. 2 shows an example of a choice set. Selected levels in alternatives of the choice set, except for price, showed additional qualitative labels and informative pictures, to ensure it was easy for respondents to understand.

2.3. Model specification

According to the random utility theory (McFadden, 1974), the utility U_{ij} provided for an individual i by an alternative j in a choice set t can be decomposed into an observed (V_{ijt}) and an unobserved part (ε_{ijt}), additively considered:

$$U_{ijt} = V_{ijt} + \varepsilon_{ijt} \tag{1}$$

where V_{ijt} is the deterministic part of the utility, which is defined by the attribute levels and the individual sociodemographic characteristics. ε_{ijt} is a stochastic error term, distributed identically and independently. Assuming V_{ijt} as a weighted sum of the attribute levels and individual characteristics, U_{ijt} can be rewritten as:

$$U_{ijt} = \beta X_{ijt} + \varepsilon_{ijt} \tag{2}$$

where X_{ijt} refers to the attribute levels and individual characteristics and β represents their associated marginal utility. The widest applied

model to estimate the utility is the conditional logit model (CL). This model assumes the error term ε_{ijt} follows an extreme value type 1 distribution (Gumbell-distribution).

However, as the utility perceived by the respondent cannot be observed, his/her choices, which can be observed, can be analysed. Thus, we can estimate the β coefficients which maximise the probability of observed choices. The probability of choosing an alternative j , ranging from 1 to J , in a choice set t , (P_{ijt}) is estimated by the maximum likelihood method (Train, 2009):

$$P_{ijt} = \frac{e^{V_{ijt}}}{\sum_{p=1}^J e^{V_{ipt}}} \quad \forall j \neq p \tag{3}$$

Thus, the utility from choosing an alternative derives from its individual characteristics and the provision of ES, which are in fact the indicators used to define the attribute alternatives (in this particular case, biodiversity, soil erosion, CO₂ balance, cultural heritage, landscape and additional cost).

Nevertheless, the CL model does imply some restrictive assumptions, the most relevant being the independence of irrelevant alternatives (IIA) and the homogeneity of the β_k coefficients across the respondents, with k being the number of attributes considered in the CE. The IIA hypothesis considers that the alternatives chosen by respondents are independent of the choice sets where they are included and this is tested by the Hausman test (Hausman and McFadden, 1984). To overcome these restrictions, the mixed logit model (MXL) is employed. The MXL model assumes that some β_k coefficients vary following a density function $\beta_k \sim f(\beta|\rho)$, where ρ is the set of parameters which describe their distribution. Thus, we assume that random β_k coefficients are normally distributed, which means ρ is the mean and standard deviation of each estimated β_k coefficient. Therefore, the functional form of the utility (U_{ijt}) derived from individual i for alternative j in the choice set t can be defined within this study as:

$$U_{ijt} = \beta_0 SQ + \beta_1 BIOD_{jt} + \beta_2 EROS_{jt} + \beta_3 CO2B_{jt} + \beta_4 CULT_{jt} + \beta_5 LAND_{jt} + \beta_6 COST_{jt} + \varepsilon_{ijt} \tag{4}$$

where β_0 is associated to the current situation (SQ), i.e., monocropping, and β_k is the marginal utility obtained from each ES k provided by the agroecosystem, reflecting how the utility level changes if the provision of ES increases. Specifically, β_1 refers to biodiversity (BIOD); β_2 and β_3 are related to regulating services (EROS and CO2B, respectively); β_4 and β_5 are related to cultural services (CULT and LAND, respectively); finally, β_6 is the coefficient for the assumed extra cost of buying food produced through crop diversification practices.

Marginal rates of substitution allow us to go deeper into social preferences analysis after estimating the model coefficients. When a cost attribute is included in the choice experiment, the marginal rate of substitution between the coefficient of non-cost attributes (β_k) and the cost attribute (β_6) shows the marginal willingness to pay (WTP) for the non-cost attributes it refers to. This is calculated as follows:

$$WTP_k = -\left(\frac{\beta_k}{\beta_6}\right) \tag{5}$$

WTP_k represents how much respondents are willing to pay in monetary terms for each ES k provided by the agroecosystem. This should be understood not only as a translation of the value of an ES, but also as a measurement of its contribution to individual wellbeing and, subsequently, of its relative importance within the overall contribution of the agroecosystem to wellbeing.

Moreover, the results obtained from the choice modelling enable the mean willingness to pay ($\overline{WTP_k}$) to be measured for each ES k , which attempts to estimate the average ES value perceived by the respondents.

Intensive food production can provide environmental impacts that can be alleviated through crop diversification practices. Crop diversification allows environmental risk reduction through an increase in biodiversity, erosion control, higher CO2 balance, and also provides a more heterogeneous landscape and the conservation of traditional knowledge and practices.

The following are proposed cropping system benefits combinations that would come with an increase in the monthly foodstuff expenditure. Please indicate your preferred option. You can also choose neither of the two proposed options. If you choose 'monocrop', you will not have to pay increased foodstuff expenditure, nor will you be avoiding current agricultural monocropping impacts. Please consider your level of disposable income before answering this question.

Scenario 1.1	Option A	Option B	Monocrop (SQ)
Biodiversity	 Low		
Soil loss	 High		
CO2 net balance	 Low		
Cultural heritage	 Absence		
Landscape	 Single crop		
Increase in household foodstuff expenditure per month	50 €	40 €	0 €
Choose an option	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Fig. 2. Example of a choice set used in the CE.

$$\overline{WTP}_k = - \left(\frac{\beta_k \overline{X}_k}{\beta_6} \right) \tag{6}$$

where \overline{X}_k represents the average level of each ES k presented in the choice experiment.

Due to the purpose of the present research, it is also of interest to measure compensating surplus (CoS) (Bennet and Blamey, 2001), which translates the welfare changes of moving from the current situation (SQ) to another different management scenario, i.e., moving from monocropping to a diversification alternative, into monetary terms. It is summarised as follows:

$$CoS_{mg_i} = - \left(\frac{V_{sq_i} - V_{mg_i}}{\beta_6} \right) \tag{7}$$

where V_{sq_i} represents the utility derived from the SQ and V_{mg_i} measures the utility associated to a specific management scenario for an individual i . Negative values for the CoS_{mg_i} imply society is willing to pay to support the aforementioned scenario.

The total economic value (TEV) provided by the agroecosystem can be calculated by aggregating the individual value of CoS_{mg_i} across all the target population. TEV_{mg} measures, therefore, the overall contribution of a specific management scenario (mg) on the social welfare. Once again assuming a linear utility function, TEV_{mg} can be estimated as follows:

$$TEV_{mg} = \sum_{r=1}^N CoS_{mg_r}, r = 1, 2, \dots, i, \dots, N \tag{8}$$

where N is the number of households of the population.

2.4. Sampling and data collection

Data were collected by trained enumerators through face-to-face questionnaires between December 2018 and January 2019. The

selected target population was of 539,000 households in the Region of Murcia, since the benefits of diversification are mainly perceived at local scale. Questionnaires were distributed through random sampling, stratified by districts within the region. The survey was performed in public places. A total of 396 surveys were carried out, which, for a 95% confidence level, provided a sample error term below 5%.

The questionnaire was structured into three parts, which comprised: (1) respondents' previous knowledge and attitudes regarding crop diversification; (2) the valuation exercise; and (3) the main socio-economic variables. Additionally, respondents' implications with agroecosystems and rural landscapes as well as their monthly expenditure on fresh fruit and vegetables were collected. Respondents were informed about the aim of the CE and the characteristics and levels of each indicator by using an information brochure and a brief cheap talk prior to starting the exercise. Cheap-talk was introduced in order to mitigate hypothetical bias of choice experiment exercise (Carlsson et al., 2005).

Table 2 shows the respondents' characteristics regarding their sociodemographic information and their relation with agriculture and compared with the average of the target population. The average age of the sample was 44 years, with a monthly household income of 2317€, and with a secondary or higher education level. t -Tests (continuous variables) and Pearson χ^2 tests (categorical variables) were carried out to analyse the representativeness of the sample. Thus, the sample was representative of the total population in terms of the main socio-demographic characteristics, mainly the age composition, gender, household income and education level.

Regarding the respondents' connection with agriculture, 42.42% had at least one family member (or indeed him/herself) working in the agricultural sector. Moreover, 79.30% of the respondents visit agroecosystems (sometimes or usually), in contrast with the 20.70% who never visit them. The main reason to frequent agroecosystems is recreation (74.52%), followed by economic activities (20.38%) and research or educational reasons (5.10%).

Table 2
Descriptive statistics.

Variable	Sample	Region of Murcia	
<i>Sociodemographic information</i>			t-Test (p-value)
Age (years)	44.31	47.90 ^a	-5.12 (0.00)
Gender (% women)	53.03	49.93 ^a	1.21 (0.23)
Household income (€/month)	2317	2325 ^b	-0.12 (0.90)
Educational level (%)			Pearson χ^2 (p-value)
Lower education	1.52	3.50 ^c	5.54 (0.14)
Primary education	8.59	16.30 ^c	
Secondary education	41.96	46.60 ^c	
Higher education	48.23	33.60 ^c	
<i>Relation with agriculture</i>			
Does any member of your family work in agriculture? (% affirmative)	42.42		
How often do you visit an agroecosystem? (%)			
Never	20.70		
Sometimes	43.69		
Usually	35.61		
If so, for what reason? (%)			
Recreation	74.52		
Economic activity	20.38		
Research/Education	5.10		

^a INE (2018a)

^b INE (2017)

^c INE (2019)

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Preference modelling

Before applying the econometric models, those surveys which showed a constant preference for the SQ alternative were analysed. In these cases, respondents did not agree with increasing their monthly expenditure on fruit and vegetables to obtain products derived from crop diversification farming. A total of 40 respondents (10.10%) chose the SQ at each choice-set, while 89.90% of respondents would be willing to pay an extra amount of money for the consumption of foodstuffs from crop diversification.

Focussing on the respondents whose preference was always SQ, 'real or legitimate' and 'non-true or protest' zeros were distinguished. Thus, real zeros do participate in the CE exercise, but they do not recognise or value the benefits -in the present study- of crop diversification, therefore they are not willing to pay extra for their foodstuffs. On the other hand, protest zeros do not participate in the hypothetical market and they disapprove of at least one part of the survey (e.g. payment vehicle). Consequently, protest zeros imply a protest behaviour which provides invalid answers (Dziegielewska and Mendelsohn, 2007). In the present work, protest zeros were identified through a follow-up question (Barrio and Loureiro, 2013). A total of 22 protest zeros were found within the whole sample. Hence, 374 individuals finally formed the hypothetical market used for the modelling.

The results obtained through the estimation of a conditional logit (CL) model are presented in Table 3, where the coefficients associated with the different attributes which make up the utility function are shown. Although all the variables are significant, the Hausman test (Hausman and McFadden, 1984) confirmed that the IIA hypothesis is rejected ($\chi^2 = 17.78$, p value = 0.01), therefore CL was considered to be unsatisfactory in preference heterogeneity modelling. Thus, the MXL model is estimated to ensure the robustness of the results. For the MXL model estimation, all non-cost attributes are treated as normally-distributed random coefficients, assuming SQ and COST as being fixed to guarantee the normal distribution of WTP (Hole, 2007). Moreover, the MXL model's goodness-of-fit is in accordance to similar studies (Ragkos and Theodoridis, 2016; Aslam et al., 2017; Niedermayr et al., 2018).

These results pointed out in the utility function show the positive impact of enhancing ES provision. The environmental benefits associated to enhancing biodiversity, reducing erosion and increasing the CO₂ balance are socially demanded, as their positive coefficients reveal

Table 3
Conditional (fixed effects) logit and mixed logit models estimated.

	CL model		MXL model	
	Coef.	SE	Coef.	SE
<i>Mean</i>				
SQ	-1.186***	0.185	-2.422***	0.329
Biodiversity	0.041***	0.004	0.078***	0.011
Erosion	0.007***	0.001	0.012***	0.002
CO ₂ balance	0.012***	0.002	0.025***	0.004
Cultural heritage	0.278***	0.058	0.558***	0.127
Diverse landscape	0.532***	0.061	1.148***	0.148
Price	-0.037***	0.004	-0.084***	0.009
<i>SD</i>				
Biodiversity			0.123***	0.015
Erosion			0.024***	0.003
CO ₂ balance			0.042***	0.005
Cultural heritage			1.175***	0.196
Diverse landscape			1.436***	0.189
N	374		374	
Log-Likelihood (LL)	-1538.48		-1353.74	
LR chi2	1029.65		369.48	
Prob > chi2	0.000		0.000	
Pseudo R2	0.251		0.341	
AIC	3090.96		2731.48	
BIC	3137.38		2811.06	

*** Statistically significant at a level of 0.01.

utility improvement for a higher level of these attributes. Moreover, the enhancement of cultural ES provided by diversification practices is also positively valued by respondents. The analysis of SD results shows heterogeneity across respondents in terms of erosion, CO₂ balance and landscape, while there is a wide consensus in considering the positive impacts of biodiversity and cultural heritage, as their non-significant SD coefficients reveal. In contrast, the price attribute has a negative sign, which involves an expected disutility perceived by respondents. The SQ attribute also shows a negative sign, which denotes a generalised desire to change the current monocropping food supply.

The ES levels proposed in different choice sets were guaranteed since they can be achieved by using intercropping or, alternatively, by other agricultural practices or technological innovations in a monocropping scenario. Indeed, alternative agricultural practices may also provide similar environmental benefits. Cover crops and green manure, reduced tillage and incorporating structural elements are some of these

environmentally beneficial practices which could also improve biodiversity, erosion control and CO₂ balance. However, they could be less cost-effective than intercropping and could even increase trade-offs among other ES (Rosa-Schleich et al., 2019). Cover crops and green manure are good practices for increasing biodiversity, erosion and weed control (Schappert et al., 2019) and carbon sequestration (Guardia et al., 2019); whereas it has not been proved that cover crops actually reduce disease incidence (Behnke and Villamil, 2019). From an economic perspective, cover crops have establishment costs, while there is not enough evidence to show a positive impact on yields (Li et al., 2019). Indeed, positive or negative changes in yield would depend on the type of crop employed as the cover crop (Rosa-Schleich et al., 2019). Reduced tillage is also an alternative practice. Even though it may enhance biodiversity, erosion control and carbon sequestration, weed control is not increased. Thus, reduced tillage will reduce costs, mainly machinery savings, but previous experiences seem to show no-impacts on yields at farm level (Langeroodi et al., 2019). Therefore, comparing all these alternative practices with intercropping, intercropping seems to be a cost-effective practice since it provides positive effects on most of the ES, while no reduction is expected in economic benefits, beyond the machinery and labour cost variations (Rosa-Schleich et al., 2019).

3.2. Willingness to pay analysis

The marginal WTP of each ES change is shown in Table 4. As expected from the results of the MXL model (Table 3), the marginal WTP for the improvement of ES provision due to crop diversification is positive. According to the MXL model, households are willing to pay 0.93 € per household and month, on average, to increase the soil microbial richness by one percentage unit. Analogously, reducing erosion rates and increasing soil organic carbon by one percentage unit would imply a WTP of 0.15 and 0.30 € per household and month, respectively. Furthermore, the respondents revealed their desire to move from the current monocropping system, specifically, they are willing to pay 28.41 €/household/month, on average, in order to support a change from monocropping to diversified agroecosystems.

Together with the results of the WTP, it is also of interest to measure the mean WTP (\bar{WTP}). The \bar{WTP} analysis shows that, on average, respondents are willing to pay a total amount of 24.58 €/household/month in order to support diversified crops. The results obtained in this case are in line with previous works on environmental non-market valuation, such as Hanley et al. (1998), although Hanley focused on the methodology and the present work delves into actual ES values. Similarly, biodiversity and landscape values as a mean are close to the results obtained by Rodríguez-Ortega et al. (2016) or Bernués et al. (2014) in Spanish Mediterranean agroecosystems. Moreover, this work points to the landscape as being an important ES and its value can be even higher than the rest, as was also shown in Dupras et al. (2017). The social value of erosion rates reduction is similar to the results obtained in mountain olive grove agroecosystems by Arriaza et al. (2008), which is relevant as that study was also carried out in Southern Spain. Rodríguez-Ortega et al. (2016) and Bernués et al. (2014) proved that people with a strong relationship with the study area were willing to pay a greater amount for its preservation than people who were not

related to that place. Therefore, the WTP high values in the present study could derive from the strong relationship of agriculture in society within the Region of Murcia: 5.1% Gross Added Value and more than 10% employment (INE, 2018b).

The WTP values obtained are higher than the results obtained by Novikova et al. (2017) and Jourdain and Vivithkeyoonvong (2017), whose works were developed in Lithuania and Thailand, respectively. Although society appreciates the importance of the ES provided by agroecosystems, the income level is significantly lower in both countries compared to mean incomes in the Region of Murcia.

3.3. Management scenarios assessment

Aromatic intercrops in rainfed almond, and legume intercrop in irrigated citrus are the feasible scenarios defined by the stakeholders for a Mediterranean agroecosystem (Diverfarming consortium, 2019). Thus, three different scenarios are proposed in the study area. These scenarios are defined as follows:

- Rainfed intercropping system (RIS). This scenario reproduces a rainfed orchard agroecosystem where intercropping is carried out. As an example, almond intercropped with *Thymus* sp. could represent this scenario. Hence, soil microbial richness is expected to increase by 7.5%, soil erosion rates would decrease by 47% and soil organic carbon would improve by 25% over monocropping. Regarding changes in cultural ES, traditional practices would continue being limited, while the landscape would be composed of multiple crops.
- Low-efficient irrigated intercropping system (LEIIS). This alternative can represent the establishing period in intercropping adoption, and even a system whereby meteorological conditions obstruct the optimal development of the soil-plant system. Here, soil microbial richness would rise by 7.5%, soil erosion rates would be reduced by 94% and soil organic carbon is expected to increase by 25% over monocropping. Moreover, the presence of traditional practices related to cultural heritage together with multiple crops would compose this intercropping landscape. This scenario represents citrus orchards intercropped with fava bean/barley.
- High-efficient irrigated intercropping system (HEIIS). This scenario could be understood as the best alternative environmentally and socially, due to the maximisation of ES provision by the agroecosystem. Thus, the environmental benefits related to intercropping would lead to a 15% increment in soil microbial richness, a 94% reduction in soil erosion rates and a 50% improvement in soil organic carbon over monocropping. Traditional practices are expected to be developed, and the landscape beauty would be established through multiple crops. This scenario can occur after a few years of citrus and fava bean/barley intercropping, when the agroecosystem has achieved good conservation status.

Compensating Surplus (CoS) and Total Economic Value (TEV) were calculated in order to compare these three scenarios. As is shown in Table 5, CoS and TEV values have been translated to positive terms within every scenario, which means respondents are willing to support a change from the SQ to any proposed scenario. In fact, both CoS and

Table 4
Willingness to Pay estimations (€/household/month).

Attribute	WTP_k	SE	[95% Conf. Int.]	\bar{WTP}_k	SE	[95% Conf. Int.]
Biodiversity (€/p.u.)	0.93	0.051	[0.83; 1.03]	4.66	0.256	[4.15; 5.16]
Erosion (€/p.u.)	0.15	0.009	[0.13; 0.17]	5.30	0.320	[4.67; 5.93]
CO ₂ balance (€/p.u.)	0.30	0.017	[0.27; 0.34]	5.71	0.319	[5.08; 6.33]
Cultural Heritage	6.97	0.410	[6.17; 7.78]	2.04	0.120	[1.80; 2.27]
Diverse landscape	13.48	0.541	[12.42; 14.54]	4.69	0.188	[4.32; 5.06]
SQ	-28.82	2.305	[-33.34; -24.30]	-28.82	2.305	[-33.34; -24.30]

Table 5
Compensating surplus^a and TEV analysis results.

Scenario	Brief description	Compensating surplus (€/household/month) Average [95% CI]	TEV (M€/month) Average [95% CI]	TEV (€/ha/year) Average [95% CI]
RIS	Rainfed intercropping system	64.09 [66.14;62.05]	34.55 [35.65;33.44]	939.83 [969.84; 909.81]
LEIS	Irrigated intercropping system throughout the establishing period	78.26 [81.06;75.47]	42.18 [43.69;40.68]	1147.62 [1188.60; 1106.63]
HEIS	Irrigated intercropping system established in the long term	92.86 [96.53;89.19]	50.05 [52.03;48.07]	1361.62 [1415.47; 1307.78]

^a Negative values from Eq. (7) have been transformed to positive in order to ease understanding.

TEV decrease as the scenarios are environmentally and socially more respectful. Thus, the HEIS scenario shows the highest value of CoS (92.86 €/household/month), while RIS has the lowest value (64.09 €/household/month). These results are similar to those of Marangon and Visintin (2006), whose results showed similar WTP estimations for the conservation of vineyards in Italy and Slovenia.

The TEV was estimated through the sum of individual CoS for the whole target population. The HEIS scenario shows the highest TEV, 50.05 M€/month, which corresponds to 600.60 M€/year for the Region of Murcia. Both this and the other scenarios' TEV reflect a strong willingness to support the protection of ES provision by agroecosystems.

Otherwise, these scenarios could be applied to different croplands. Furthermore, in the Region of Murcia, the TEV was applied to the total cropped surface area, including both rainfed and irrigated farmlands, and also herbaceous and tree orchard lands. These results, also shown in Table 5, confirm that the ES value can be higher than that of market products for society (Sandhu et al., 2008), especially in low profitable crops, such as the rainfed almond crop, whose annual gross margin is around 500 €/ha/year (Zabala et al., 2018).

In this context, regarding the social valuation for more sustainable agricultural practices scenarios, the previous results could be compared to policy initiatives related to crop diversification and other practices to empower agricultural ES. Therefore, in Europe, the latest CAP reform determined *greening* initiatives to promote natural resources conservation, on top of some specific volunteer agri-environment schemes included in the established rural development programs. These initiatives apply an amount that can reach 30% of the direct payment in the case of greening and recover the foregone benefits associated to the specific agri-environmental practices (priorities 4 and 5 for the case study are financed by 60% of the CAP second pillar budget). In the Region of Murcia, *greening* subsidies range from 46.37 €/ha/year (137.29 €/ha/year when considering the whole direct payment including the greening subsidy) in rainfed crops to 113.33 €/ha/year (335.54 €/ha/year when considering the whole direct payment including the greening subsidy) in irrigated crops (BOE, 2014, 2016). Compared to the results, the social valuation of intercropping practices is higher than the subsidy perceived by farmers. Therefore, if the socioeconomic value represented by the WTP results were destined to farmers directly, there would still be room to compensate farmers. Maintaining the current distribution of the CAP budget, this means a considerable increase from four to seven times the current direct payment subsidy amount. This could be a greater support to promote crop diversification practices that should be considered in future CAP reforms, given the existing social demand for the provision of such environmental goods.

However, the design of optimal payments to support intercropping needs to deal not only with environmental and social benefits (non-market valuation) but also with farm level economic analysis (market valuation). Market valuation allows one to value provisioning ES, which accounts for farm benefits and costs produced by adopting intercropping practices by farmers. Extra income due to a secondary crop is expected, although this could be associated to a change in the main crop production (which can decrease or even increase if synergies between crops are optimized). Experiences to date reveal that intercropping does not seem to reduce main crop yields, and may even increase them (e.g. Pelzer et al., 2012; Mercenaro et al., 2014; Pantera et al.,

2018). On the other hand, maintaining two crops involves extra costs which should be considered equally. For instance, intercropping practices may reduce machinery and labour (Rosa-Schleich et al., 2019). Thus, further research is needed to better understand the farm-level economic effects of intercropping and integrate them into a complete cost-benefit analysis, which considers both market and non-market valuations of agricultural practice to set long-term sustainable agroecosystems.

CAP payments would allow farmers to not only obtain the economic incentives to promote the adoption of intercropping practices (Dessart et al., 2019). As the results claim, people are willing to pay for the consumption of food coming from intercropping. However, it would be necessary to communicate to society as to how this typology of agriculture provides such public goods. Eco-labelling could be an effective strategy to deal with it in order to play a major role in consumers' food choices (Grunert et al., 2014). To integrate eco-labels throughout the food supply chain is also a challenge for increasing such agricultural practices (Miranda-Ackerman and Azzaro-Pantel, 2017). Furthermore, alternative food networks, such as short food supply chains, may also be another way to increase social awareness regarding the benefits of intercropping based on the direct interaction between farmers and consumers (Zoll et al., 2018).

Crop diversification can be implemented in a variety of forms and at a variety of scales, allowing farmers to choose a strategy that both increases resilience and provides economic benefits (Lin, 2011). As Scown et al. (2019) point out, the evaluation of management options and scenarios in agricultural systems, with a broad stakeholder vision, is called upon to play a key role in the design of sustainable agricultural land systems in Europe.

4. Conclusions

This study proves that society is aware of cultural and environmental externalities derived from agroecosystems in a semi-arid Mediterranean area. Moreover, people recognise the variety of benefits provided by an intercropping agricultural system. As a matter of fact, cultural and regulation ES enhanced by the intercropping system are relevant services which are highly demanded by the society. High non-market values of considered attributes point out the importance of considering agricultural policies not only from a financial approach but also from a holistic one, also including environmental and cultural services.

Highly-efficient crop diversification is the most valued alternative, as environmental and social benefits are maximised. The TEV (1361.62 €/ha/year) value is in fact potentially higher than the crop financial benefits, in some cases of low profitable farmlands, such as almond crops. Therefore, adopting diversification practices at farm level would imply a social benefit at regional scale, promoting food security, environmental health, etc.

However, although crop diversification has been encouraged by the CAP, intercropping practice is limited to small family-run farms whose aim is household consumption or organic agriculture. In this framework, the results obtained in the present study are useful to guide agricultural policies. Sustainable agroecosystems and enhancing Ecosystem Services provision are demanded by society, despite this

entailing an increase in fruit and vegetables prices. Thus, our results show that environmentally focused policies would be accepted by society. From this starting point, it would be interesting to delve into a wider economic analysis to include the crop diversification market and non-market benefits. Hence, integrating crop diversification contributions to society from a holistic approach could confirm this practice to be a good alternative to intensive monocropping, exploring more sustainable farming options. Crop diversification is shown to be a cost-effective method to build resilience into farming systems as adaptive management for environment change.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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